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Revisiting Law and Order in the rule of king Mattakala as depicted in Dasakumaracaritam

Muthuselvi A¹

Abstract

The Sanskrit narrative titled “*Dasakumaracaritam*,” written by Dandin, belongs to the 7th century AD. This narrative describes the adventures of ten princes among them, the first is Somadatta. Somadatta went to Ujjayini, where he got information about the conflict between the king Viraketu of Ujjayini and king Mattakala of Lata. In between he was arrested by the soldiers of the king of Lata without proper inquiry. This arrest gives rise to questions about the condition of law and order under the rule of king Mattakala of Lata as to how soldiers can arrest anyone without proper enquiry, if the law and order is properly maintained. This research intends to study different dimensions of the issue. For this complete narrative of king Mattakala and his soldiers shall be revisited.

Key words: Law and order - *Dasakumaracaritam* - Duty of a Ruler - King Mattakala - Somadatta - conflict - Treasure - Messenger.

Introduction

Law and order are the establishment and enforcement of laws to maintain a safe and structured society and that is why it is considered as the backbone of a nation. The law includes the rules and regulations governing every aspect of society, along with procedures and punishments for violations to ensure proper functioning and stability in the country. Law and order are very essential to decrease the crime rate and punish criminals for disturbing the harmony in

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the country, which encourages people to live morally and peacefully.

From ancient times to modern times, rulers are the most responsible persons for the implementation and protection of law and order in their countries. Law enforcement agencies, including the police are responsible for upholding the laws, protecting citizens, investigating crimes, bringing criminals to justice, and maintaining peace in the country. The rulers are required to check their governing bodies to ensure that they fulfill their duties properly.

But, due to the improper functioning of the Government, people suffer a lot. A similar incident happens in the kingdom of Mattakala described in the third chapter of *Dasakumaracaritam* where the ruler fails to govern in the right way. This study aims to analyze the governance of King Mattakala, which leads to the failure of the protection of law and order.

The rule of king Mattakala as depicted in dasakumaracaritam

The third chapter of *Dasakumaracaritam* describes the adventurous conquest of Somadatta, one of its ten heroes. King Mattakala of the Lata country requested King Veraketu of Ujjayini to bestow his daughter, Vamalochana, to him but he refused the proposal, which made King Mattakala furiously besiege the capital of Ujjayini and forcefully made King Viraketu surrender his daughter to him. In order to save the princess, Minister Manapala ordered his servants to create a subterranean passage to King Mattakala's apartment and kill King Mattakala for her rescue but when they entered the palace, the king had departed for hunting. The disappointed soldiers stole the treasure and escaped into the deep forest because they couldn't return with empty hands. King Mattakala's soldiers caught them by their footprints, and they found out that one of the valuable jewels was missing, and Somadatta was pointed out as a thief by a Brahmana surrounded by soldiers. The Brahmana was released, and Somadatta was arrested by the soldiers without any inquiry and they didn't try to hear the words of Somadatta, who had just given the jewel found by him from the riverside by chance to the Brahmana as a donation. Somadatta and the ministers' servants escaped to the minister's camp. King Mattakala sent a messenger to Minister Manapala to hand over the thieves to the king; otherwise, destruction would happen, but the minister refused it with rage. King Mattakala attacked with a

few soldiers against the army of Minister Manapala. Somadatta, a skilled warrior, unleashed a rain of arrows on King Mattakala's side, preventing them from advancing further. Subsequently, Somadatta leaped onto King Mattakala's chariot and beheaded him. Mattakala was defeated and killed.

Discussion

Wrongful Arrest:

Wrongful arrest or false arrest is an unlawful tort of imprisoning an innocent person. For arresting a person, a proper inquiry must be undertaken with reference to their involvement in the crime, sufficient evidence, the person's statement, statements of witnesses, etc. Here, the arrest of the Brahmana might be correct as he was found with the jewel, but the arrest of Somadatta as a thief based solely on the words of the Brahmana cannot be considered correct. Without the statement of the accused, Somadatta, he was imprisoned and confirmed as the thief of the lost jewel. Soldiers didn't conduct a proper investigation by not asking any questions like "where did you get the jewel?" and "where are you from?". These essential inquiries would have helped establish the truth behind the alleged theft and could have provided crucial information to determine innocence. This shows a lack of investigation.

The fact that the Brahmana was eventually released and Somadatta arrested could suggest that the soldiers acted hastily without thoroughly examining the evidence. Such arbitrary decisions indicate a lack of proper functioning of law enforcement and judicial procedures. The incidents raise serious concerns about the state of law and order in the country of Lata during King Mattakala's reign. The mistreatment of Brahmana, who was innocent and the mishandling of the theft accusation indicates that there was no proper investigation. People might have lost trust in the justice system. This could cause unrest and dissatisfaction among the people and led to protest and loss of peace inside the country.

Similarly, an incident mentioned in the Tamil text titled *Silapathikaram*, written by Ilango Adigal, belongs to the late 2nd A.D. Kovalan, the hero of the text, is wrongly accused of stealing the anklet of Queen Kopperundevi, the Pandyan queen. In reality, it was his wife Kannagi's anklet that he tried to sell to a merchant

to get out of his poor situation. The merchant framed him as a thief and reported to the Pandya king Nedunjeliyan I. The pandya king ordered hastily to the soldiers to execute him without the proper inquiry. (Dikshitar 2021).

Consequences of Treasury Looting:

The treasury is the reservoir of a nation's wealth because it manages financial resources, supports economic stability and funds public services. The treasury of a nation is filled by the taxes and duties from the people, military conquest, confiscation for unlawful acts, vassal tribute, etc and hence, valuable wealth should be properly protected with high security measures. But, due to the negligence of King Mattakala to protect the treasury properly, the treasury was looted by the servants of Manapala in his absence. The safety of the hard work of people in the form of wealth in treasure was not properly ensured under the rule of King Mattakala. The king should have checked whether his officers were undertaking their duties, but King Mattakala didn't inspect the protection of his treasury. He also didn't punish the soldiers who did not guard the treasure well.

Diplomatic Missteps of Sending an Inappropriate Messenger:

A messenger should convey the information of his king to the receiver with proper qualities like reliability, skilled communication, diplomacy, neutrality, physical and emotional resilience, etc. Conveying the message of the king harshly with pride would instigate enmity more. The messenger of King Mattakala spoke the message with pride to Minister Manapala, demanding that the thieves be handed over to the king, or else destruction would happen. This act of the incapable messenger made Minister Manapala refuse with fury.

Making hauteur decisions in matters of war:

A ruler should not underestimate the enemy's strength, and he should analyze the weaknesses and strengths of the enemy and their allies too before the strike. Haughty decisions led him into the hands of defeat. 'Anger may in time change to gladness; vexation may be succeeded by content. But a kingdom that has once been destroyed can never come into being again; nor can the dead ever be brought back to life' (Giles 2000: 58). The haughty decision about the battle against Minister Manapala, without considering his army's

power and his allies, led him to the destruction of his kingship. An army that initiates the first attack has more opportunities to win the battle.

Conclusion:

The law and order of King Mattakala clearly shows the consequences of an irresponsible and haughty ruler who made hasty decisions, didn't punish the soldiers for improper inquiries, and lacked safety arrangements, which caused the destruction of his rule. A ruler must be conscious of his decisions, analyze whether his actions would support the welfare of the country or not, and should not act out of pride. The wrong act of a ruler not only affects him but also affects his country.

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